

Environmental Monitoring with Visuo-Haptic Augmented Reality UAV Teleoperation

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Abstract—We report the field evaluation of a haptic guidance system for Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) in the context of environmental monitoring tasks. In the proposed system, the operator receives a haptic feedback based on the real-time measured intensity of the substance of interest. The haptic system, supplemented with visual cues integrated in an Augmented Reality interface, has been tested in monitoring tasks in relevant and operational environments. It has shown its potential to reduce the exploration time of large areas, as well as to decrease the mental fatigue experienced by the operator teleoperating the UAV in critical tasks.

Keywords—component, formatting, style, styling

I. INTRODUCTION

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) and Remotely-Piloted Aerial Systems (RPAS) have great potential for monitoring tasks, thanks to their ability to fly at low altitude, loiter, and approach closely to areas of interest. Current notable UAV-based monitoring applications include facility visual inspection for wear assessment in structural engineering (e.g. bridges) [1], evaluation of crop ripeness and irrigation needs in precision agriculture [2], and search of biological-chemical-radiation hazards and spillovers for environmental protection or recovery [3].

Monitoring applications require that the UAV be equipped with suitable exteroceptive sensors for the substance or physical quantity of interest. Examples of such exteroceptive sensors are multispectral and IR cameras commonly used onboard the UAVs to assess a vegetation index or soil temperature, as well as smart noses to detect various substances. Based on the specific setup and use case, sensor data can be stored in a local memory onboard, together with the UAV position, along a pre-planned navigation route and then offloaded at the base station at the end of the flight. Alternatively, sensor data can be transmitted in real-time to a base station during the monitoring task using a dedicated communication channel (supplementing the one dedicated to remote control and user command of the UAV). The latter configuration has the advantage of enabling a faster reaction from the operator and the adaptation of the UAV monitoring and navigation plan based on the sensor data collected so far.

It should be mentioned that performing an environmental monitoring task with a UAV is not always akin to recording photographs or videos in a leisure event. Environmental monitoring tasks are often *mission critical* (e.g., the risk of losing a whole crop production) or *safety critical* (e.g., to assess the spillover of a dangerous chemical substance). Hence, in most UAV environmental monitoring operations

the flight is actually supervised by one, or more often a team of, human operators so as to ensure both a correct and safe operation of the flight and a timely execution of the proper decisions and recovery actions based on the outcome of the monitoring activity.

II. ISSUES IN ENVIRONMENTAL MONITORING WITH UAVS

Small multicopter UAVs offer the ability to station (loiter) above selected areas of interest, and hence to perform a careful local exploration, which is a great advantage in environmental and situational monitoring [3]. Their main drawback is the limited flight duration, typically in the order of a few tens of minutes or less. This issue is exacerbated by the need to carry a non-negligible payload comprising the sensing unit, which may require additional onboard processing and communication equipment. The required payload is typically in the order of several 100 g up to a few kg. Indeed, the use of sensors such as standard Geiger counters and electronic noses is precluded by their weight. Due to the overall weight of vehicle + payload, UAVs for environmental monitoring are likely required (by existing regulations) to be equipped with a parachute or other safety equipment, thereby further reducing their flight autonomy.

The limited UAV flight duration is especially detrimental in critical operations such as hazard identification and detection in large areas, such as industrial large factories, customs premises, wasteland, natural preserves. When environmental emergencies arise in these areas, finding polluting sources may entail many consecutive UAV flights, battery swaps, off-line analyses of logged data. Incorporating real-time sensor feedback from the field into user guidance is a way to augment the operator's intelligence and domain experience for faster detection and accurate characterization of environmental factors, yet without exposing the operator to potential risks.

III. HAPTICS-BASED UAV GUIDANCE

To cope with the issue of limited UAV flight duration we have developed a haptics-based guidance system wherein the operator receives a real-time haptic feedback based on the measured intensity of the substance or quantity of interest. The systems has been patented [4],[5] and has been integrated into an augmented reality interface [6] where visual clues extracted from a fixed camera further assist the operator in proper guiding the UAV toward the position of maximal detection. Since for many physical quantities of interest the measured quantity is inversely related to the distance to the emitting source, maximizing the measured substance detection implies guiding the UAV as close as possible to the emitting location [7], and possibly identifying

the emitting source or part based on prior knowledge or additional sensors (e.g. a supplementary onboard camera).

In practice, the UAV is set to fly at a fixed height via the standard remote controller. The operator specifies horizontal heading directions, based on his/her domain knowledge of areas to be monitored, by moving the haptic device. If the substance or quantity of interest is measured with a value above the given threshold, the haptic device returns a force feedback opposing to commands that would drive the UAV to an area with a lower returned value. In this way, the operator is assisted in driving the UAV to a position where the measurement is maximized. The point of emission is therefore assumed to be just below the final UAV loitering position. Full details of the proposed haptics-based guidance systems, based on an impedance control mode, are reported in [4-7].

Fig. 1 shows the operator interacting with the 3DOF haptic interface (Novint Falcon) and the octocopter UAV used in the experiments summarized in the next section.

Fig. 1. The haptic guidance interface with the Novint Falcon and the Virtual Robotix 4-axis octocopter with its sensor payload.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

The novel haptics-based guidance system has been tested with an UAV (by Virtual Robotix) equipped with a lightweight Gamma-ray spectrometer for detection and identification of radioactive materials (Fig. 1, right) [8]. The sensing unit is an advanced lightweight CdZnTe X-ray detector weighing about 0.3 Kg and featuring a low power consumption and a measurable energy range from 10 KeV to 1.3 MeV, with radioactivity counts on 4096 energy bands. These data are received at the base station and fed into the haptic interface with a delay of about 2.2 s due to sensor reading and data transmission from the onboard microcontroller.

Initial tests of the haptic guidance system have been carried out with multiple users where the UAV was required to localize simulated emitting sources (in locations unknown to the operator). These tests have shown the benefits of the approach in reducing the time required to localize the point of emission, in improving the accuracy of localization, as well as in keeping the operator focused on the UAV guidance by reducing his/her visual load thanks to the additional sensory channel provided by haptics [9]. These advantages imply the potential for a significant reduction in the time needed to localize hazardous sources in large areas, especially compared to a brute force, systematic exploration of the area, requiring multiple UAV flights with battery replacement in between.

Additional tests have been performed in relevant environments (TRL6) and operational environments (TRL7), including tests with real radioactive emitting sources carried out in open areas under the supervision of the Regional

Agency for Environmental Protection of Regione Emilia-Romagna (ARPAE). Indeed, tests with actual radiating sources are rather complex to set up due to the required safety norms. These tests have confirmed the effectiveness of the visuo-haptic interface as well as a significant improvement of the situational awareness of the operator [6], which implies a decreased likelihood of errors in critical tasks.

Fig. 2. The haptic-guided UAV surveying an actual waste landfill to search for any radioactive waste (e.g. hospital waste) mixed with standard solid urban waste.

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